

Placeholder Name of the conference

Placeholder Session title

© Authors. This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License

Synergy in Life Sciences

Joint strategies and services for national and European collaboration between NFDI consortia

Christian Busse¹ <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7553-905X>,
Barbara Ebert² <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3328-6693>,
Frank Ewert³ <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4392-8154>,
Juliane Fluck^{4,*} <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1379-7023>,
Konrad U. Förstner⁴ <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1481-2996>,
Oliver Kohlbacher^{5,6} <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1739-4598>,
Björn Usadel⁷ <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0921-8041>,
and Stefanie Weidtkamp-Peters⁸ <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7734-3771>

¹ German Cancer Research Center (DKFZ), Heidelberg, Germany (<https://ror.org/04cdgtt98>)

² GFBio - German Federation for Biological Data e.V., Bremen, Germany (<https://ror.org/02qtnz251>)

³ Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research, Müncheberg, Germany (<https://ror.org/01ygyzs83>)

⁴ ZB MED - Information Centre for Life Sciences, Cologne, Germany (<https://ror.org/0259fwx54>)

⁵ University of Tübingen, Germany (<https://ror.org/03a1kwz48>)

⁶ University Hospital Tübingen, Germany (<https://ror.org/00pjgqh97>)

⁷ Forschungszentrum Jülich, Jülich, Germany (<https://ror.org/02nv7yv05>)

⁸ Heinrich Heine University Düsseldorf, Düsseldorf, Germany (<https://ror.org/024z2rq82>)

*Correspondence: Juliane Fluck, fluck@zbmed.de

Abstract

There are currently 26 domain-specific consortia in the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI), eight of which are in the field of life sciences: DataPlant [1], [2], FAIRagro [3], [4], GHGA [5], [6], NFDI4Biodiversity [7], [8], NFDI4BioImage [9], [10], NFDI4Health [11], [12], NFDI4Immuno [13], [14] and NFDI4Microbiota [15], [16]. These consortia address key aspects of research data management in their respective domains of life sciences.

Various consortia clusters actively pursue the shared vision of 'oneNFDI' through collaborative activities. A few examples highlight the growing formalisation of these interactions: a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) was signed in 2024 between the 'biodata consortia' NFDI4Biodiversity, NFDI4Microbiota and DataPLANT [17] and between the health-data focused consortia NFDI4Health and GHGA [18]. The consortia of the Biodata Interest Group agreed on joint activities based on similarities in data types, scientific methods and common infrastructures. The biomedical consortia GHGA, NFDI4BioImage, NFDI4Health, NFDI4Immuno and NFDI4Microbiota also identified key topics for collaboration at a first joint Biomed workshop in November [19] and have been in regular dialogue since then. Additionally, all consortia are part of the Geo-Chem-Life Science Helpdesk Cluster facilitating interdisciplinary user support.

This workshop builds on these and other common initiatives and provides a forum for the systematic development of joint lines of action within the life sciences consortia. The aim is to make synergies visible at national and European level and to agree on initial lines of action to shape closer strategic and operational collaboration.

Topics to be addressed:

- What are the key challenges for integrated and interdisciplinary research in the life sciences?
- How can engagement within the designated research communities be strengthened?
- Where are the overlaps in services, infrastructures or standards?
- Which topics are suitable for coordinated activities or joint offerings?
- How can the visibility of our NFDI services be increased on different levels – e.g. towards scientific communities and at local institution in European initiatives (ELIXIR, ESOC) or political stakeholders?
- How can funding bodies be engaged to support consolidation and standardisation in the field by clearly communicating current challenges and ensuring they are reflected in future funding programs?

The workshop is designed as a moderated plenary discussion. After a short introduction by representatives of the three clusters (Biodata Interest Group, Biomed cluster, Bio-Geo-Chem helpdesk cluster), key areas of cooperation will be presented and discussed together. The aim is not only to make existing collaborations more visible, but also to identify the need for new collaborations, possibly also with external partners. As a result of the workshop, first lines of action will be identified to further enhance cross-consortia coordination and consolidation of national and European activities and projects.

The workshop is aimed at representatives from all life science disciplines who wish to contribute to the discussion on possible synergies and cross-cutting collaborations.

Keywords: SIO: biological data, SIO: medical data, SIO: bioinformatics data, T4FS: research data management infrastructure, T4FS: research data management

Author contributions

All authors contributed on writing the original draft and reviewed and edited the submitted abstract.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Funding

- DataPLANT: "Funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG) - project number 442077441"
- FAIRagro: "Funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG) - project number 501899475"
- GHGA: "Funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG) - project number 441914366"
- NFDI4Biodiversity: "Funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG) - project number 442032008"
- NFDI4BIOIMAGE: "Funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG) - project number 501864659"
- NFDI4Health: "Funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG) - project number 442326535"
- NFDI4Immuno: "Funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG) - project number 501875662"
- NFDI4Microbiota: "Funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG) - project number 460129525"

Acknowledgement

We acknowledge the support of FAIRagro, GHGA, NFDI4Biodiversity, NFDI4BIOIMAGE, NFDI4Health, NFDI4Immuno, NFDI4Microbiota and DataPLANT as part of the German National Research Data Infrastructure.

References

- [1] T. Mühlhaus *et al.*, "DataPLANT – Tools and Services to structure the Data Jungle for fundamental plant researchers," in *E-Science-Tage 2021*, heiBOOKS, 2022. doi: 10.11588/HEIBOOKS.979.C13724.
- [2] "DataPLANT Website." Accessed: Apr. 16, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nfdi4plants.org/>
- [3] X. Specka *et al.*, "FAIRagro: Ein Konsortium in der Nationalen Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (NFDI) für Forschungsdaten in der Agrosystemforschung: Herausforderungen und Lösungsansätze für den Aufbau einer FAIRen Forschungsdateninfrastruktur," *Informatik Spektrum*, vol. 46, no. 1, pp. 24–35, 2023, doi: 10.1007/s00287-022-01520-w.
- [4] M. König, "FAIRagro Website." Accessed: Apr. 16, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://fairagro.net/>
- [5] J. Eufinger, J. Korb, O. Kohlbacher, and O. Stegle, "Bausteine Forschungsdatenmanagement : 2021, 2Genomdaten FAIR und sicher teilen: Das Deutsche Humangenom-Phänom Archiv (GHGA) als Baustein der Nationalen Forschungsdateninfrastruktur," 2021, doi: 10.17192/BFDM.2021.2.8349.
- [6] "GHGA Website." Accessed: Apr. 16, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ghga.de/>
- [7] F. O. Glöckner *et al.*, "NFDI4BioDiversity - A Consortium for the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI)," 2020, doi: 10.5281/ZENODO.3943645.
- [8] "NFDI4Biodiversity Website," NFDI4Biodiversity. Accessed: Apr. 16, 2025. [Online]. Available: <http://nfdi4biodiversity.org/de/>
- [9] J. Moore *et al.*, "NFDI4BIOIMAGE - National Research Data Infrastructure for Microscopy and Bioimage Analysis," 2024, doi: 10.5281/ZENODO.13168693.
- [10] "NFDI4BIOIMAGE Website." Accessed: Apr. 16, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://nfdi4bioimage.de/home/>
- [11] J. Fluck *et al.*, "Bausteine Forschungsdatenmanagement : 2021, 2NFDI4Health – Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur für personenbezogene Gesundheitsdaten," 2021, doi: 10.17192/BFDM.2021.2.8331.

- [12] M. Vivone, "NFDI4Health Website," NFDI4Health. Accessed: Apr. 16, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nfdi4health.de/en/>
- [13] C. E. Busse, "NFDI4Immuno - National Research Data Infrastructure for Immunology", doi: 10.5281/zenodo.15233115.
- [14] "NFDI4Immuno Website." Accessed: Apr. 16, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nfdi4immuno.de/>
- [15] K. U. Förstner *et al.*, "NFDI4Microbiota – national research data infrastructure for microbiota research," *RIO*, vol. 9, p. e110501, 2023, doi: 10.3897/rio.9.e110501.
- [16] ["NFDI4Microbiota-Website." Accessed: Apr. 16, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://nfdi4microbiota.de/>
- [17] K. Förstner, B. Ebert, F.-O. Glöckner, D. von Suchodoletz, A. C. McHardy, and T. Mühlhaus, "Memorandum of Understanding between NFDI4Biodiversity, NFDI4Microbiota and DataPlant," 2024, *Zenodo*. doi: 10.5281/ZENODO.13880944.
- [18] K. Deschler *et al.*, "Memorandum of Understanding between NFDI4Health and GHGA," 2024, *Zenodo*. doi: 10.5281/ZENODO.12799244.
- [19] C. Busse, "The NFDI BioMed Interest Group - A report from the 2024 workshop", 2025, CORDI submitted.
- [20] L. Bernard *et al.*, "Memorandum of Understanding of NFDI consortia from Earth-, Chemical and Life Sciences to support a network called the Geo-Chem-Life Science Helpdesk Cluster," 2025, *Zenodo*. doi: 10.5281/ZENODO.15065070.